

Leifeng Pagoda (Leifeng ta 雷峰塔)

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Buddhist Traditions, Chinese Buddhist Traditions, Religious Place, China, Hangzhou, Zhejiang, West Lake 西湖

The Leifeng Pagoda was constructed between 971 and 977 under Qian Chu 錢俶 (r. 948-978), then-ruler of the state of Wuyue 吳越, on the shores of West Lake in Hangzhou (present-day Zhejiang province). In its original construction, the pagoda was a seven-story, octagonal structure with an interior core of brick and exterior corridors and double eaves made of wood. Beneath the structure, an underground chamber was built to house the relics of "locks of the Buddha's hair" (Fo luokuo fa 佛螺髻髮). After sustaining damage, the Leifeng pagoda was reconstructed during the Qingyuan 慶元 era (1195-1200) of the Southern Song dynasty, when it was reduced to a five-story structure. During this time, the pagoda also gained its literary status as one of the "famous sites of Hangzhou," under the title "Rays of Sunset at Leifeng" (雷峰夕照). During the Jiajing 嘉靖 era (1522-1566) of the Ming dynasty, the wooden exterior of the pagoda was burned away, and its silhouette became known to visitors by its exposed brick core. Throughout this period and thereafter, the pagoda became known not primarily as a Wu-Yue pagoda, but for its association with "The White Snake Legend" (白蛇傳), in which it served as the site where the "White Maiden" (白娘子) was locked away. In 1924, the brick core of the pagoda finally collapsed. The site remained in a state of ruin until March, 2000, when the two-year archaeological excavation of the site began. Undisturbed upon excavation, the pagoda's underground chamber was found to contain fifty-one objects, including nested reliquaries, Buddhist sculptures, a gilded silver belt, jewelry, jade and glass objects, coins, mirrors, and Buddhist texts. It is believed that, in the upper part of the pagoda, an additional chamber was built to house another set of reliquaries and objects. In some parts of the pagoda body, hollow bricks were used in construction. Many of these bricks originally housed printed scrolls of the "Dhāranī Sūtra of the Seal on the Casket" (寶篋印陀羅尼經), many of which were collected when the pagoda collapsed in 1924. The current pagoda building at the site of Leifeng, completed in 2002, is a five-story, octagonal pagoda reconstructed to resemble the Southern Song structure.

Date Range: 971 CE - 2022 CE

Region: West Lake

Region tags: China, Zhejiang, Hangzhou

West Lake in the city of Hangzhou, Zhejiang Province

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Qian Shuoyou, comp. Xianchun Lin'an zhi (Gazetteer of Lin'an during the Xianchun reign). 1265-1274. Vol. 490 of Yingyin Wenyuange siku quanshu. Reprint, Taipei: Taiwan shangwu yinshuaguan,

1983–1986.

- Source 2: Li Yuxin, ed. *Leifeng yizhen (Relics of Leifeng)*. Beijing: Wenwu chubanshe, 2002.
- Source 3: Zhejiang sheng wenwu kaogu yanjiusuo (Cultural Relics and Archaeology Institute of Zhejiang Province). *Leifeng ta yizhi (The Leifeng Pagoda Site)*. Beijing: Wenwu chubanshe, 2005.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.zhejiangmuseum.com/Collection/ExcellentCollection>
- Source 1 Description: Searchable collection of Zhejiang Provincial Museum, where objects excavated from Leifeng Pagoda are housed.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Notes: In 1924, the badly-damaged pagoda, then nearly 950 years old, collapsed at its site on the southern shore of West Lake. Following the collapse, the pagoda's hollow bricks were found to contain printed scrolls of a Buddhist dharani sutra. These scrolls were collected and sold by amateur enthusiasts. Authentic and forged examples exist in collections across the world. It was not until 2000, however, in the midst of a reconstruction project, that the pagoda's foundation and underground chamber were archaeologically excavated. The first report resulting from this excavation was published in 2002 in "Cultural Relics" (Wenwu).

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 2000-2001

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Cultural Relics and Archaeology Institute of Zhejiang Province excavation of Leifeng Pagoda site

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Body of water (as distinct from source)

Notes: The pagoda was built on the southern shore of Hangzhou's West Lake.

– Elevation

↳ Type of elevation

– Mountain

Notes: The name Leifeng ("Thunder Peak") refers to the site's hilly elevation near the Nanping Mountains south of West Lake.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Trackway or road-surface

Notes: Historical records from the Xianchun Lin'an zhi indicate that the pagoda was originally accompanied by a courtyard. The archaeological excavation has also revealed remnants of paths, stairs, and Buddhist halls surrounding the pagoda's foundation.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: Given its elevated position south of West Lake, Leifeng Pagoda was posed to be visible, across the lake, from urban Hangzhou. In the centuries following its completion, the pagoda also gained canonical status as one of the "Ten Views" of the city, under the appellation "Leifeng Pagoda in Evening Glow." Leifeng Pagoda also became associated with the large Buddhist Monastery, Jingci, located south of the pagoda, which was established in 954. From the time of its construction in the tenth century until the present day, the Leifeng Pagoda has remained a significant feature in the physical and, later, literary landscapes of the city.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: The site has never been far from urban Hangzhou, but writers of successive generations have, by

turns, emphasized or de-emphasized the Buddhist character of the pagoda itself. Starting in the sixteenth century, the pagoda became associated increasingly with a folkloric story centered on the romance between a young man and a snake-turned-woman, later known as "The White Snake Legend" (Bai she zhuan).

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Other [specify]: Octagonal

Notes: According to a dedicatory inscription discovered during the excavation, the original pagoda was designed to be thirteen stories tall. Financial constraints, however, limited the builders to a seven-story octagonal structure. The current, reconstructed pagoda is a five-story octagonal structure, designed to emulate the style of pagoda as it appear after renovations during the Song-dynasty.

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: No

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

Notes: Based on a stele text, a postface to the Flower Garland Sutra (Huayanjing), excavated at the site that was originally installed in the interior walls of the pagoda, scholars have been able

to reconstruct the motivations for the pagoda's construction. The postface records how the pagoda was constructed to house locks of the Buddha's hair in the possession of a person from the royal palace of the Wu-Yue Kingdom. Qian Chu, then-ruler of Wu-Yue, had the relics deposited within Leifeng Pagoda in order to allow for public, rather than private, devotion. Reconstructions of the pagoda suggest that it originally featured circumambulatory passages, through which visitors could encircle the pagoda.

↳ Worship:

– Communal

– Memorial

Notes: The aforementioned postface to the Flower Garland Sutra excavated at the site also records that the original name of the pagoda was "Pagoda of the Imperial Consort" (Huangfei ta). This name suggests that the pagoda was constructed to commemorate the consort of Qian Chu, Sun Tianzhen, who died in 977.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Notes: The construction of pagodas during this period often revolved around an implicit or explicit intention to preserve relics of the Buddha, or of eminent monks. The presence of underground and aboveground deposit chambers in the Leifeng Pagoda, built to house relics and offerings to them, indicate that this intention existed for its tenth-century patrons.

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: In the centuries after its completion in 977, the Leifeng Pagoda fell into disrepair. From 1195 to 1200, the pagoda underwent a major reconstruction, during which it was reduced from seven-story structure to a five-story structure. In the mid-sixteenth century, the pagoda was damaged by pirates in the Hangzhou area. During this time, the outer wooden structure was burned away and only the pagoda's brick core remained. The remnant brick structure itself became a landmark of the Hangzhou region until the early twentieth century. In 1924, the brick structure finally collapsed. From 2000 to 2002, the current pagoda was reconstructed in the style of the five-story Song pagoda.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

- Burned
- Collapsed

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:
– As the result of pillage

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:
– Human-caused accident
– Natural phenomena

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
– Yes

↳ In antiquity
– More than once

↳ In modernity
– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:
– No

Notes: Only in the sense that the pagoda was built to house the corporeal remains of the Sakyamuni Buddha (locks of the Buddha's hair).

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:
– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:
– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:
A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.
– Yes

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

Notes: The Leifeng Pagoda was commissioned by Qian Chu, ruler of the Kingdom of Wu-Yue.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– I don't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Notes: The stone stele postface to the Flower Garland Sutra discovered at the site records the initial donation by the ruler Qian Chu to construct the pagoda. Designed initially as a thirteen-story structure, the pagoda was eventually built in seven stories due to lack of funds. Personal items donated by elites of the Wu-Yue Kingdom were also found within the pagoda and attest to a possible involvement of non-royal donors in funding the construction.

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Notes: In a more general sense, the devotional practices surrounding relic worship were likely intended, in part, to generate "merit," the power to alter one's own or other's lives through good deeds.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– Yes

What type of scriptures/sacred texts [specify]:

– Type: Buddhist dharani sutras

Notes: At Leifeng Pagoda, the upper stories of the pagoda were constructed by special hollow bricks designed to house rolled-up woodblock-printed scrolls of the Dharani Sutra of the Seal

on the Casket (Baoqieyin tuoluoni jing), dated 975. These texts were discovered not during the 2000 reconstruction, but during the 1924 collapse of the pagoda. At that time, more than 1,000 prints were reported found among the pagoda's ruins. Forged copies began to circulate widely thereafter. All scrolls begin with a dedication by Qian Chu and a frontispiece illustration.

↳ Were the scriptures/sacred texts located in a specific room within the main structure:

– No

↳ Where are the scriptures/sacred texts located in secondary building:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures actively used at the place:

– No

Notes: The printed dharani texts were housed inside hollow bricks and so not capable of being read after the construction of the pagoda was complete. However, we can still think of the prints as being "in use" in this context. Dharani prints were thought to be able to function on several different registers, depending on their context, including as relics of the Buddha's teaching equivalent to corporeal relics, and as talismans.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– I don't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 1000

Notes: The foundation of the original pagoda is octagonal, with sides measuring around fifteen

meters. A 5.7-5.9-meter wide veranda encircled the foundation. Square footage of successive stories would have decreased incrementally as one ascended the pagoda.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 68

Notes: 68 meters is the estimated height of the seven-story Leifeng Pagoda upon its completion in 977. The original plan for the pagoda, according to a stele inscription excavated at the site, was a much larger thirteen-story structure, around 200 meters tall. The height of the reconstructed pagoda is 71 meters (9.8-meter base, 45.8-meter body, 16.1-meter spire).

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Metal

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

–Yes [specify]: Brick and tile

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: Architectural features that are structural in nature were also decorated at Leifeng Pagoda, including eaves tiles. Excavated has revealed several decorative features that would have been visible from the outside of the pagoda and within its surrounding veranda, including stone sculptures of waves and mountains at the pagoda's foundation, ceramic sculptures, and incised stone slabs with calligraphy and pictorial images.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: The appearance of the inside of the Leifeng Pagoda as it stood upon completion is difficult to reconstruct from the ruins. Archaeological excavation has discovered several stone, metal, and ceramic sculptures that may have once been installed inside the pagoda's upper stories.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: Stone carvings at the pagoda's foundation are decorated with an abstracted representation of mountains and seas, common in pagoda bases of the period.

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Notes: There are floral motifs along the borders of the inscribed stone slabs and on the ends of eaves tiles.

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: Archaeological excavation discovered 1,104 stone fragments of inscribed stone at Leifeng Pagoda. Most of the fragments comprise the Flower Garland Sutra and the Diamond Sutra.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Architectural

Notes: One of the stone fragments discovered at Leifeng depicts the corner of a multi-story architecture set among trees, possibly depicting the Leifeng Pagoda itself.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Much of the original appearance of the Leifeng Pagoda can be reconstructed only through conjecture. It is likely that parts of the decoration could only be seen as one ascended the pagoda.

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

Notes: Several statues of Buddhist deities have been discovered both among the ruins of the pagoda's foundation and within the underground chamber. Those discovered among the ruins were likely deposited in the upper stories of the pagoda.

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Statues of protective deities and of supernatural creatures were excavated.

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: Statues of both monks and of devotees have been discovered.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: None

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Landscape

Notes: The decorations of mountains and seas at the pagoda's foundation are carved in stone relief.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: A stone stele discovered at the site records the circumstances of the reconstruction of the pagoda from 1195 to 1200. The back of this stele records the names of donors who donated land.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Notes: The postface to the Flower Garland Sutra stele, composed by Qian Chu, offers the dedication for the site and describes the circumstances of its construction in the 970s.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: None

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Because the pagoda body collapsed in 1924, having devolved into a state of serious disrepair before that, and archaeological excavation of the site did not begin in earnest until 2000, much of the original decorative and sculptural program of Leifeng Pagoda is lost. Information about the pagoda's decoration comes mainly from the excavated foundation, bricks, and the underground chamber built to house the assemblage of relics and donated objects.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: In Buddhist practice, pagoda construction (and stupa construction) originally possessed a function akin to that of a reliquary, and was thus connected to the worship of the remains of a Buddha. In various times and places, this function was complemented by a commemorative function, especially with pagodas or stupas were erected at sites associated with the life of the Buddha. In China, pagoda architecture existed as a tradition distinct from tomb construction in China, yet, as many archaeologists have noted, the worship of Buddhist relics has variously drawn from and influenced forms of funerary worship. The decoration and arrangement of pagoda architecture is thus often thought of fruitfully as expressing the form of a kind of tomb or burial for the remains of the Buddha. Sites like Leifeng Pagoda, either implicitly or explicitly, combine this funerary function of pagoda worship with the commemorative function of recording the geographic dispersal and rediscovery of the Buddha's relics in China.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Notes: Only in the limited sense, that upon death the Sakyamuni Buddha entered nirvana, and pagoda architecture serves as a locus for the worship of the Buddha's relics.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Excavated texts at the Leifeng Pagoda indicate that the pagoda was constructed to house the corporeal relics of the Sakyamuni Buddha.

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: None

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– Yes

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Notes: The worship of Buddhist relics, as it developed in the Hangzhou region during the tenth century, almost always involved the deposit of valuable offerings by laypeople and monks. Many of these objects are inscribed with votive dedications, expressing the wishes of their donors, most often for favorable rebirth either for themselves or for family members.

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: Material offerings to relics in China continued the tradition of offering valuable objects to relics known as the "Seven Treasures" (七寶), which are defined variously in different times and places. Material offerings are often valuable in the sense of being made from expensive luxury materials like gold, silver, lacquer, mother-of-pearl, and pearls, or being crafted and decorated with high levels of craftsmanship. In other pagodas in this region, material offerings appear to have gained their value through their status as personal possessions rather than through their luxury, or market exchange, value.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Daily-life objects comprise a minority of the material offerings. Most are valuable pieces of silver jewelry, including bracelets and hairpins, one of which was inscribed with a dedication by its donors, Wang Luo and a woman surnamed Hu. An additional gilded silver belt, donated by a certain Chen Chengyu, may have been worn by its donor in life. In addition, 3,428 coins were excavated at this site.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

Notes: 51 material offerings at Leifeng Pagoda were deposited inside an underground chamber beneath the center of the pagoda. This deposit was relatively small (60cm wide and 72cm deep) and sealed with a stone covering. Most of the underground deposit space was occupied by an iron box, which housed the reliquary and several material offerings. Additional material offerings were placed in the chamber outside the iron box. The excavation of the site also uncovered several material offerings, including an additional reliquary, among the pagoda's ruins. Archaeologists believe these offerings were originally housed in an aboveground chamber within the pagoda's body. In general, offerings would not have been accessible after deposit.

Other

–Other [specify]: None

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– No

Notes: In the centuries after it was constructed, the Leifeng Pagoda fell into disrepair and was not ritually maintained. The structure was repaired or reconstructed intermittently throughout its history, most recently from 2000 to 2002.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– No

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– Yes

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:

– Yes

Notes: The texts of the Flower Garland Sutra (Huayan jing), the Diamond Sutra (Jin'gang jing), and the Dharani of Great Compassion (Dabei zhou) were among the texts selected to be displayed on the eight sides of the ground story of the pagoda, incised on stone slabs. Archaeologists suggest that the stone slabs with incised texts were installed in both the interior and exterior of the ground floor around the pagoda's veranda.

↳ Housed within the place/structure:

– Yes

Notes: The specially designed hollow bricks that comprised the upper stories of the pagoda once held scrolls of the Dharani Sutra of the Seal on the Casket, printed in 975.

↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):

– Yes

Notes: A postface on the Flower Garland Sutra is a text composed by Qian Chu relating the origin of the pagoda's construction.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: None

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